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Temperature Distribution Analysis and Conduction Simulation in Rotary Furnace Walls Using ANSYS Software

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Abstract

This study focuses on the analysis of temperature distribution and conduction simulation on the walls of a Rotary Kiln used in the production of cast iron. The Rotary Kiln, a crucial element in the metal casting industry, utilizes diesel fuel as its primary source of energy and operates at temperatures up to 1500°C. The dual objectives of this research are to map the furnace wall temperature profile with high precision using ANSYS numerical simulation software, and to determine the heat transfer coefficients for the inner and outer surfaces of the furnace wall. The methodology involves collecting detailed specifications of the furnace, creating a finite element analysis (FEA) model using ANSYS, and conducting an in-depth thermal evaluation including the simulation of actual operational conditions. Simulation results indicate a maximum temperature of 1499.4°C inside the furnace, decreasing to 1332.5°C at the interface of the fire-resistant cement wall, and drastically dropping to 101.69°C on the outer surface of the firebrick wall. Further analysis reveals that a significant temperature drop occurs within the firebrick layer itself. These findings highlight the impressive thermal efficiency of the furnace wall construction and underscore the importance of selecting appropriate materials and construction techniques in furnace design to enhance safety and efficiency. This research not only deepens the understanding of thermal dynamics within industrial furnaces but also has the potential to improve operational efficiency, contributing to more sustainable and cost-effective industrial practices.

Keywords: *Rotary Kiln Thermal Analysis; Cast Iron Production Simulation; ANSYS Numerical Modeling; Furnace Wall Temperature Distribution; Heat Transfer Coefficient Evaluation*

Introduction

The Rotary Furnace is a crucial component in the metal casting industry, distinguished by its unique cast iron melting technique with a rotating working principle. This industrial furnace employs diesel oil as its primary fuel source, capable of sustaining a working temperature of up to 1500 degrees Celsius[1]. Moreover, it boasts an impressive capacity, allowing for the melting of up to 1 ton of material per tapping cycle. The primary application of this furnace is the melting of gray iron castings, primarily composed of Fe₃C. To better understand the design and dimensions of the Rotary Furnace, Figures 1 and 2 provide a visual representation of its equipment and size, respectively[2]. These visual aids serve as invaluable references for engineers and technicians operating or maintaining this specialized machinery[3]. The Rotary Furnace stands as a pivotal element within the foundry industry due to its innovative rotating working principle, robust fuel efficiency, and substantial

melting capacity[4]. It plays a critical role in the production of gray iron castings, making it an indispensable asset for metallurgical processes in various industrial applications[5].

In the realm of engineering and thermal sciences, it is essential to identify and comprehend the known variables associated with a given system or apparatus. In the context of the specified furnace, several critical parameters have been established: The combustion chamber temperature (T_{cc}) is rigorously maintained at a searing 1500 degrees Celsius, while the combustion chamber itself boasts a diameter (D_{cc}) of 0.84 meters. The outer wall of the furnace (D_{outer}) has a broader diameter of 1.5 meters, with a substantial wall thickness (T_{wall}) of 330 millimeters, contributing to its structural integrity and thermal insulation[6]. The surrounding environmental temperature (T_{env}) in the vicinity of the furnace is recorded at 38 degrees Celsius. The furnace's wall is composed of two distinct materials, with a 30-millimeter layer of concrete cement material on the exterior and a thicker 300-millimeter layer of fire brick material on the interior, serving to insulate and protect the furnace. The total length of the furnace walls (L_{wall}) extends for 2 meters, defining the overall dimensions of the furnace structure[7]. Understanding and meticulously monitoring these known variables are indispensable for the precise operation and maintenance of the furnace while ensuring its safety and efficiency in various industrial applications. These parameters lay the foundation for rigorous analysis and optimization of the furnace's performance and thermal characteristics[8].

Figure 1: Cast Iron Rotary Furnace

Figure 2: Cast Iron Rotary Furnace dimensions

In the process of analyzing a furnace's thermal performance, a critical aspect to consider is the quantification of heat loss (Q) occurring through its various wall components. To comprehensively assess and mitigate this heat loss, it becomes imperative to delve into the temperatures associated with different sections of the furnace walls[9]. Specifically, this analysis necessitates the examination of three distinct temperature parameters: the inner wall surface temperature (t_1), the temperatures within wall layers 1 and 2 (t_2), and finally, the surface temperature of the outer wall (t_3)[10]. Firstly, the inner wall surface temperature (t_1) denotes the temperature at the immediate interior surface of the furnace wall. This temperature holds significance as it directly interfaces with the furnace's contents and can affect the efficiency of the heating process. Secondly, temperatures within wall layers 1 and 2 (t_2) are of paramount interest. These layers comprise different materials, with varying thermal properties, and their respective temperatures impact the overall heat transfer characteristics of the furnace. Lastly, the surface temperature of the outer wall (t_3) holds importance due to its exposure to the external environment[11]. It plays a pivotal role in determining the insulation efficiency and structural integrity of the furnace. In summary, this analysis aims to quantify heat loss (Q) by investigating the temperatures of t_1 , t_2 , and t_3 , thereby providing essential insights into the thermal behavior of the furnace walls. By understanding these temperature parameters, engineers and researchers can make informed decisions to enhance the furnace's efficiency, reduce energy consumption, and optimize its overall performance[12].

Figure 3 shows the thermal conduction and convection mechanism on the walls of the Cast Iron Rotary Furnace. The radii r_1 , r_2 , and r_3 represent the progressive layers of the furnace wall, from the innermost (r_1) to the outermost (r_3). The coefficients h_i and h_o denote the convective heat transfer coefficients on the inside and outside of the furnace, respectively. These coefficients quantify the rate of heat transfer between the furnace wall and the surrounding fluids, which could be air or another medium, with h_i pertaining to the internal furnace environment and h_o to the external environment[13]. The temperatures t_1 , t_2 , and t_3 correspond to the thermal states at each respective layer, starting from the inner wall (t_1) and moving outward (t_3), with t_{f2} representing the ambient temperature. The conductive heat transfer through the furnace wall is governed by the coefficient's k_b and k_c , which represent the thermal conductivities of the inner and outer wall materials, respectively. These coefficients define how well the materials can conduct heat, with a higher value indicating better heat conduction[14]. The heat energy Q is the total energy being transferred out of the system. It flows through the wall by conduction, driven by the temperature gradient between the interior (t_1) and the exterior (t_3), and is then dissipated into the surroundings by convection, as indicated by h_o and the ambient temperature t_{f2} [15]. The bottom part of the image shows a simplified representation of the heat transfer path from the interior to the exterior surface of the furnace wall. This is characterized by a series of resistances to heat flow, analogous to electrical resistors, which include both conductive and convective resistance elements denoted by R_a , R_b , R_c , and R_d . These resistances are a function of the material's thermal conductivity and thickness, as well as the convective heat transfer coefficients. The arrangement illustrates how the heat transfer is a multi-step process, requiring consideration of both conduction within the wall and convection on the boundaries[16].

Figure 3: The analogy of electrical resistance to wall heat propagation

In this rigorous study, we conceptualize each stratum of the furnace wall as an electrical resistor, serving to decelerate the transference of heat from the fervent core to the cooler external surface. This conceptual framework is critical for quantifying the rate of thermal energy dissipation. Employing Equation (1), we determine this rate (Q), taking into account t_{f1} - the temperature of the fluid within the furnace's heart, t_{f2} - the temperature gracing the wall's outermost facade, and R_r - the aggregate thermal resistance encapsulating the wall's reluctance to heat passage. To further dissect the intricacies of heat escape, Equation (2) is deployed, deriving the total resistance due to convection[17]. In this expression, h epitomizes the film coefficient of convection - a measure of the convective heat transfer per unit area and temperature difference, while A symbolizes the surface area, the theater of thermal exchange. Moreover, the resistance that arises from the very act of conduction is appraised using Equation (3). In this context, d marks the thickness of each individual layer, L the longitudinal span of the furnace, and k the thermal conductivity - a material constant that defines its ability to conduct heat[18]. Collectively, these equations form a robust mathematical apparatus, empowering analysts to meticulously chart the path of heat through the furnace's anatomy. Such quantification is not merely academic; it is a beacon that illuminates the understanding of thermal dynamics, with profound implications for the enhancement of energy efficiency and the optimization of furnace design within industrial settings[19].

$$Q = \frac{t_{f1} - t_{f2}}{R_r} \quad (1)$$

$$R_a = \frac{1}{h_1 A_1} \quad (2)$$

$$R_b = \frac{\ln \frac{d_2}{d_1}}{2\pi L K_b} \quad (3)$$

This research was driven by a dual purpose. The first goal was to map out the temperature profile across the furnace wall with high precision, leveraging the advanced computational prowess of ANSYS software for numerical simulation. Such detailed modeling is crucial for pinpointing areas of thermal variance that could affect furnace performance. The second goal was to meticulously determine the heat transfer coefficients for the furnace

wall's inner and outer surfaces. These coefficients are vital for quantifying the intensity and efficiency of heat exchange. Together, these objectives are fundamental not only to deepen our grasp of the thermal dynamics in industrial furnaces but also to potentially improve their operational efficiency, thereby contributing to more sustainable and cost-effective industrial practices.

Methodology

The details pertaining to the rotary furnace type cast iron machine utilized in this research project were acquired through official documentation provided by the equipment manufacturer. These specifications, crucial for the study's accuracy and reliability, have been conveniently summarized in Table 1 for easy reference and accessibility. Table 1, presented herein, offers a comprehensive overview of the machine's key specifications, encompassing essential parameters such as its dimensions, operational capabilities, and materials of construction. These specifications not only serve as a valuable resource for researchers and technicians involved in the project but also act as a benchmark for quality control and adherence to industry standards. The inclusion of these specifications aligns with the best practices of research transparency and reproducibility, as it enables other scholars and professionals in the field to replicate and verify the experimental setup. Furthermore, it fosters a deeper understanding of the equipment's capabilities, aiding in the interpretation of research results and their wider applicability in industrial settings. In essence, this meticulous approach to documenting and presenting equipment specifications enhances the rigor and credibility of the research conducted using the rotary furnace type cast iron machine.

Table 1: Specifications of cast iron making machine with rotary furnace type

Name	Unit	Value
Diameter of the inside of the furnace (d1)	m	0.84
The outer diameter of refractory cement (d2)	m	0.9
Outer diameter of refractory bricks (d3)	m	1.5
Thermal conductivity of refractory cement (kb)	W/m.K	1.0
Thermal conductivity of refractory bricks (kc)	W/m.K	1.0
Convection coefficient in the furnace (hi)	W/m ² .K	10,000
Convection coefficient outside the furnace (ho)	W/m ² .K	50

Utilizing the information presented in Table 1 as a foundation, the construction of the rotary furnace model was undertaken with the assistance of the Ansys software package. The outcomes of this modeling endeavor are thoughtfully illustrated in Figure 4. This research effort involved the creation of a finite analysis model, a crucial step in generating a detailed representation of the furnace system, which is discretized into smaller, manageable units known as "Mesh." Each unit or mesh, as employed in this study, possesses a length of 75 mm. To ensure the accuracy and effectiveness of the analysis, a suitable element type was chosen, namely the triangular mesh type. This selection aligns with the specific requirements of the analysis and optimizes the computational process. Figure 5 provides a visual representation of the arrangement of these mesh elements within the furnace model. This visualization elucidates the meticulous and systematic approach taken in modeling the furnace's intricate structure, facilitating a deeper understanding of its thermal behavior and structural dynamics. The utilization of Ansys software, in conjunction with the finite analysis model and the strategic deployment of triangular mesh elements, underscores the rigor and precision of this study's approach to examining the rotary furnace. This methodology not only

enhances the accuracy of the results but also serves as a valuable framework for future research and engineering applications in the field.

Figure 4: Modeling of the rotary furnace wall

Figure 5: Mesh modeling of rotary furnace walls

In the realm of finite element analysis, it is customary to treat all external influences as loads, and in this context, temperature is regarded as one such load. In this particular analysis, the temperature load consists of two components. Firstly, there is the internal temperature originating from within the furnace, which is an intense 1500 degrees Celsius. Additionally, there exists an external temperature load on the outer surface of the furnace wall, primarily attributed to convection heat transfer, with a magnitude of 37 degrees Celsius. This temperature load, a pivotal aspect of the analysis, is meticulously incorporated into the model, as visually represented in Figure 6. The purpose of this step is to simulate the real-world thermal conditions experienced by the furnace during its operation accurately. By including both the internal and external temperature loads, the finite element analysis strives to emulate the complex thermal interactions within and around the furnace structure, enabling a comprehensive assessment of its performance under various thermal stresses and conditions. In essence, this approach facilitates a deeper understanding of how temperature affects the structural integrity and behavior of the furnace, and it is a fundamental component of the finite element analysis process, contributing to the precision and reliability of the study's findings.

Figure 6: Temperature modelling in rotary furnaces

Result and Discussion

Table 2 provides an overview of the heat resistance calculations for each furnace wall in our study. The furnace under investigation has specific dimensions, with an internal diameter of 0.84 meters. It consists of multiple layers, with the innermost layer being constructed from fire-resistant cement, having an outer diameter of 0.9 meters. The outermost layer is comprised of fire-resistant bricks and has an outer diameter of 1.5 meters. It is essential to note that both the fire-resistant cement and brick walls possess identical thermal conductivities, measuring 1.0 W/m.K. The convection coefficients inside and outside the furnace are 10,000 W/m².K and 50 W/m².K, respectively.

Table 2: Results of finite element calculations on heat transfer in the walls of the Rotary Furnace

Calculation components	Unit	Value
Cross-sectional area of the inner furnace (A1)	m ²	5.275
Cross-sectional area of refractory cement part (A2)	m ²	5.650
Cross-sectional area of refractory brick section (A3)	m ²	9.420
Heat resistance in the furnace (Ra)	K/W	1.895e-5
Thermal resistance of fireproof cement walls (Rb)	K/W	0.0055
Thermal resistance of refractory brick walls (Rc)	K/W	0.0406
Thermal resistance on the outside of the furnace wall (Rd)	K/W	0.0021
Heat loss rate at the outer wall of the furnace (Q)	kW	30.332
Temperature inside the furnace (t ₁)	°C	1499.4
Temperature at the wall interface (t ₂)	°C	1332.5
Temperature on the outside of the furnace wall (t ₃)	°C	101.69

The results from our simulations reveal crucial insights into the temperature distribution within the furnace. The furnace's interior reaches a maximum temperature of 1499.4 °C. Moving closer to the walls, the temperature at the interface of the fire-resistant cement wall is 1332.5 °C, whereas the temperature on the exterior surface of the fire-resistant brick wall is significantly lower, at 101.69 °C. This substantial temperature drop across the furnace walls showcases the impressive thermal efficiency of the wall construction. Further analysis using Ansys software indicates that the most significant temperature decrease occurs within the fire-resistant brick wall itself. Specifically, the temperature decreases significantly from 1313.99 °C at the interface between the fire-resistant cement and brick to 95 °C on the exterior of the fire-resistant brick wall. This substantial temperature difference underscores the critical role played by the fire-resistant brick wall in reducing temperatures, thereby minimizing the risk of damage to external structures and preventing unnecessary heat loss. These findings highlight the importance of choosing appropriate materials and construction techniques in furnace design to enhance safety and efficiency.

In Figure 7, we present the outcomes of an extensive Finite Element Analysis (FEA) simulation, conducted using Ansys software, to meticulously evaluate the temperature distribution within a rotary furnace employed in the production of cast iron. The simulation results unveil a remarkable temperature gradient that exists from the furnace's interior to its exterior. This particular furnace is constructed with a complex multi-layered wall structure consisting of an inner layer composed of refractory cement and an outer layer comprised of refractory brick. To provide context, the interior chamber of the furnace boasts a diameter of 0.84 meters. The refractory cement wall has an outer diameter measuring 0.9 meters, while the external diameter of the refractory brick wall expands to 1.5 meters.

The simulation itself yields a strikingly high temperature reading within the innermost region of the furnace, peaking at a scorching $1499.98\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This temperature reading underscores the exceptionally harsh operating conditions characteristic of iron production furnaces. As we move toward the interface between the refractory cement and brick layers, the temperature registers at $1408.88\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, revealing a relatively modest temperature decrease of $91.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ from the inner cement wall to the interface. However, a significant drop in temperature becomes evident as we reach the outer surface of the brick wall, plummeting to a mere $95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This observation highlights the exceptional thermal insulating properties of the selected materials and their critical role in preserving the structural integrity of the external furnace wall. The color-coded visualization accompanying the simulation effectively illustrates this temperature gradient, with red regions signifying elevated temperatures and blue zones indicating cooler temperatures, thus providing an intuitive representation of heat transfer dynamics within the intricate furnace wall structure.

Figure 7: FEA simulation results for heat transfer on the rotary furnace wall

Conclusion

The simulation results using ANSYS software exhibit a highly variable temperature distribution throughout the furnace. It was found that the maximum temperature inside the furnace reaches 1499.4°C, decreasing to 1332.5°C at the interface of the fire-resistant cement wall, and further dropping to a much lower 101.69°C on the outer surface of the firebrick wall. This indicates a significant temperature reduction within the firebrick layer itself, underscoring the remarkable thermal efficiency of the furnace wall construction. The conclusion of this study asserts that the selection of appropriate materials and construction techniques is crucial in the design of furnaces to enhance safety and efficiency. The high thermal efficiency of the furnace wall contributes to reducing the risk of damage to external structures and avoiding unnecessary heat loss. Therefore, this research not only enhances the understanding of thermal dynamics in industrial furnaces but also has the potential to improve operational efficiency and contribute to more sustainable and cost-effective industrial practices. These conclusions can guide the improvement of design and operation of furnaces in the metal casting industry and provide a foundation for further research into the thermal optimization of industrial equipment.

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Amir Syam, (1) 1 (2024), Temperature Distribution Analysis and Conduction Simulation...

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